

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

No. 8

New Zealand: Major shellfish poisoning (NSP) in early '93

In early January 1993 in Whangarei, an unusual number of human illnesses was reported after consumption of shellfish. This marked the first case, ever substantiated in the region, of shellfish poisoning symptoms caused by eating contaminated shellfish. Many more cases of shellfish poisoning were subsequently reported to the Health Authorities, from areas to the north and south of Whangarei, stretching from the North Cape to the East Cape of northern North Island.

In mid-January, after the general public had been alerted to the toxic outbreaks, the first PSP-producing dinoflagellate, *Alexandrium minutum*, was identified from samples collected in Bay of Plenty. This

species was immediately implicated as the culprit of the shellfish poisonings. A second species, *A. tamarense*, was also found in the Bay of Plenty area, but at very low concentrations. In late January, shellfish harvests were completely banned throughout New Zealand. The loss in export sales was estimated to be NZ \$ 2 million per week.

The majority of more than 180 confirmed cases of shellfish poisoning suffered symptoms such as numbness of lips, tingling fingers, reversed sensation to hot and cold, muscular weakness, nausea, diarrhoea, and vomiting, most of which are symptoms more typically associated with

(Cont'd on p. 2)

Sampling locations around New Zealand between January and May 1993.

Harmful blooms of *Leptocylindrus minimus* in Southern Chile

In November 1989 in the centre and south of the Chiloe Archipelago, high concentrations of *Leptocylindrus minimus* were detected and unusual behavior and mortalities observed in trout and salmon⁽¹⁾. A literature search and enquiries amongst foreign investigators indicated that this diatom has had no harmful effects elsewhere in the world. It thus seemed to be a local problem only, that high concentrations of *L. minimus* can cause problems for

cultured salmonids. We have no evidence of the mechanisms involved but suspect that the diatom causes mechanical problems in the gills.

The same species was again very abundant in October 1993 in Estero Castro and Lemuy Channel, i.e. in the same localities as in 1989, and unusual behavior and deaths of salmonids occurred again. Last summer (December 1993, January 1994), blooms were also found in Caicaen

Channel and near Quellon.

Water samples are collected following the protocol of the phytoplankton monitoring programme of the Chilean Salmon and Trout Producers Association⁽²⁾, and further samples are received from affected farms. Some results for *L. minimus* are given in table I.

The effects on fish are as follows. Salmon retire to the corners of their cages while trout swim right at the surface with their dorsal fins out of the water. The gills may be slightly pale in salmon, and there may be mucus secretion. There is loss of appetite, especially in trout, but also in salmon and coho. These effects are seen at cell concentrations below 10,000 cells ml⁻¹. At higher concentrations, deaths can occur.

Table I: *L. minimus* blooms in Southern Chile – counts in cells ml⁻¹ for surface samples

Place	Date	<i>L. minimus</i>	Total phyto.	Secchi, m	Note
Castro/Lemuy/Yal	3-9 Nov. 1989	35000			(i)
Cailin	24 Nov. 1989	29770	30223	3.5	
Castro/Lemuy	7-18 Oct. 1993	17500	18945	2.5	
Caicean Channel	13-25 Oct. 1993	1961	6161	3.5	(ii)
Caicean Channel	15-30 Dec. 1993	854	1230	6.0	(iii)
Isla Coldita	4-16 Jan. 1994	33024	34195	1.5	(iv)
Cailin	9-24 Jan. 1994	4446	4514	6.0	(iv)

(i) Mortality, especially among trout; (ii) No harm to salmonids noted; (iii) Despite low concentrations, damage to salmon gills occurred; (iv) large aggregations of medusae seen.

(1) Clément, A. and G. Lembeye, 1993a. Phytoplankton Monitoring Program in the Fish farming Region of the South of Chile. In: Toxic Phytoplankton Blooms in the Sea; (Eds. Smayda, T. and Shimizu); pp. 223-228.

(2) Clément, A. and G. Lembeye, 1993b. Programa de Monitoreo y Vigilancia de Fitoplancton. Informe Técnico # 2. Asoc. de Prod. de Salmón y Trucha de Chile (A.G.); Puerto Montt, Chile.

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neurotoxic shellfish poisoning (NSP). As no NSP-producing organism had yet been identified, there was some confusion as to the cause of the January illness.

It was not until mid-February that a new *Gymnodinium breve*-like species was identified by the New Zealand Oceanographic Institute (NIWA - Marine). This *breve*-like *Gymnodinium* species was detected after complaints of respiratory irritation from several hundred residents and students visiting the Whangaparoa and Red Beach areas, north of Auckland. Subsequently samples received by Dr. Lincoln MacKenzie, Cawthron Institute, from Coromandel, further south of Auckland city, also revealed the presence of the same organism.

Soon after the identification of this new *Gymnodinium* species, lipid extracts from shellfish were tested positive for NSP by the New Zealand Communicable Disease Center (NZ CDC). Toxin analyses of New Zealand shellfish carried out by Prof. T. Yasumoto, Tohoku University, Japan, showed that there is a new class or classes of polyether compounds, similar but not identical to brevetoxins. *Gymnodinium breve*, found in the Gulf of Mexico and Florida, is the only species known to produce brevetoxins (potent neurotoxins). Dr. M. Poli of the Toxinology Division at the US Army, Maryland, USA, also confirmed by radio-immunoassay the presence of a brevetoxin-like chemical in New Zealand shellfish extracts.

Until now NSP outbreaks have been largely confined to the Atlantic coast of the USA. It is significant that the 1993 shellfish poisoning was the first major outbreak recorded in New Zealand, and is also the first major outbreak of NSP poisoning to be reported outside the Atlantic coast of the USA.

During the early 1993 toxic shellfish outbreaks, NSP toxins were found mainly on the northeast coast of North Island. This coincided with the distribution of the new *Gymnodinium breve*-like species (max. concentration 1.80×10^5 cells.l⁻¹). Shellfish extracts which have been analyzed quantitatively for NSP by the NZ CDC, showed levels ranging from 23 to 592 MU 100 g⁻¹ shellfish tissue. The threshold level for NSP is set at 20 MU 100 g⁻¹ in the USA, and this has been used as a guideline by the NZ CDC to close shellfish harvests ever since NSP was detected in summer 1993 in New Zealand.

Although NSP comprised the major toxic outbreak in early 1993, a moderate to low level of PSP was also detected by the NZ CDC on the northeast coast of North Island. The PSP levels ranged from 39 to 412 µg PSP equiv. 100 g⁻¹ shellfish tissue.

However, the majority of toxicity tests showed levels between 100 to 200 µg PSP equiv. 100 g⁻¹ shellfish tissues, which is slightly over the threshold level 80 µg PSP equiv. 100 g⁻¹. In the early 1993 episode, PSP did not appear to pose much of a problem to human health. Two clonal cultures of *A. minutum* developed at the New Zealand Oceanographic Institute

were found. These are listed in Table 1. Most of these species were quite sporadic in distribution and occurred in low concentrations. Low levels of DSP (<0.5 µg OA g⁻¹) and ASP (<19 µg DA 100 g⁻¹) were detected by the Environmental Health and Forensic Sciences in several areas around the northeast coast of North Island. These toxins did not appear to have caused any problem to human health during the toxic episode.

Between February and May 1993, several major blooms were also reported in many areas around New Zealand. Most of these blooms were harmless and were dominated mainly by a few common dinoflagellate and diatom species, and a photosynthetic ciliate, *Myrionecta rubra* (= *Mesodinium rubrum*) (Table 2). The surface discoloration caused by the build-up of these organisms ranged from brown, or reddish brown to red. Blooms of coccolithophores were also observed by Dr. MacKenzie during aerial surveys in Marlborough Sounds and Big Glory Bay in South Island in early 1993.

The early 1993 toxic algal events coincided with a prolonged period of unusual climatic conditions, an effect of El Niño. This was the second major algal event to coincide with El Niño in the last decade in New Zealand. The recent

episode is distinct from the previous one in 1983, as outbreaks of shellfish poisoning were not a feature of the earlier event.

The El Niño event appeared to continue through 1993, but there are now signs of weakening of this event since the end of 1993. So far only low concentrations (<1000 cells.l⁻¹) of *Gymnodinium breve*-like species have been found since August 1993, in Hauraki Gulf, on the northeast coast of North

Island, and smaller amounts of NSP detected in shellfish in the same areas this summer compared with 1993. There are also far less areas being closed to shellfish harvesting this year. Because shellfish in New Zealand have regularly been tested for toxicity, and swift action taken by the newly established Marine Biotoxin Unit, Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, to close shellfish harvesting whenever toxins have been detected higher than accepted threshold levels, cases of shellfish poisoning appear to have been prevented this year.

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Table 1
Toxic and potentially harmful phytoplankton species identified during the early 1993 toxic shellfish outbreak, and type of toxins known to be produced by these organisms

Phytoplankton taxa	Type of toxins
<i>Gymnodinium</i> sp. nov. (cf. <i>breve</i>)	NSP
<i>Alexandrium minutum</i>	PSP
<i>A. tamarense</i>	PSP
<i>Dinophysis acuminata</i>	DSP
<i>D. acuta</i>	DSP
<i>D. fortii</i>	DSP
<i>D. tripos</i>	DSP
<i>Prorocentrum lima</i>	DSP
<i>Pseudnitzschia pungens</i> f. <i>pungens</i>	Non-toxic
<i>P. australis</i>	ASP
<i>Chrysolochromulina</i> cf. <i>polylepis</i>	Fish-killing
<i>Gymnodinium mikimotoi</i>	Fish-killing
<i>Heterosigma akashiwo</i>	Fish-killing
<i>Prorocentrum minutum</i>	Hepatotoxin

Table 2
Predominant species identified in blooms between February and May, 1993

Date	Dominant species	Bloom colouration	Location
17 Feb.	<i>Myrionecta rubra</i>	Reddish-brown*	New Plymouth
18 Feb.	<i>Prorocentrum micans</i>	Brown*	Lake Ellesmere
2 March	<i>Prorocentrum triestinum</i> / <i>Gymnodinium sanguineum</i>	Reddish-brown*	Timaru
10 March	<i>Myrionecta rubra</i>	Reddish-brown*	Timaru
24 March	<i>Myrionecta rubra</i>	Reddish-brown*	New Plymouth
2 April	<i>Asterionella glacialis</i>	Brown	Invercargill
18 May	<i>Chaetoceros armatum</i> / <i>Aulaciscus</i> sp.	Brown	Muriwai

* Sighted by Air New Zealand pilots

were subsequently tested for PSP.

Like the new *Gymnodinium breve*-like species, *A. minutum* was predominantly found on the northeast coast of North Island, with a smaller incidence on the southeast coast of South Island. The bulk of this species appeared to occur in Bay of Plenty (max. concentration 1.17×10^5 cells.l⁻¹), coinciding with moderate levels of PSP detected in the same areas. This species is similar to the *Alexandrium* species previously isolated by Dr. Vivienne Cooper from Whangarei Harbour in 1983, but no PSP outbreak was reported then.

At the height of the toxic events, several other toxic and potentially harmful species of phytoplankton were simultaneously identified in areas where new *Gymnodinium* species and *A. minutum*

Sixth International Conference on Toxic Marine Phytoplankton

This event assembled 273 registered participants and some occasional visitors, in all about 300 persons from more than 40 countries, during five days of plenary sessions and round table discussions. Four scientific themes were explored: the mechanisms of harmful bloom formation, identification and detection of responsible species, cellular biochemistry and physiology, and bioaccumulation effects of phycotoxins. These themes were treated in oral communications and 160 posters, while round table discussions were devoted to subjects previously given less consideration, such as toxic Cyanobacteria blooms and the ecology of benthic dinoflagellates.

Mechanisms of harmful bloom formation

This session dealt with the theory of a global spread of blooms and outbreaks as indicated by models, trend studies and consideration of human activities and associations between microalgae and bacteria.

Some models presented can be applied on a global scale, e. g. the role of winds and weather of the southern Benguela (South Africa), the effects of advection and diffusion within and adjacent to the rias of northwest Spain and front dynamics at the entry to the Gulf of Finland. Trend studies, such as those carried out in France using data from the national monitoring network, indicate large-scale geographical specification of populations. On a regional scale, the factors involved in bloom dynamics are variable: the role of light intensity and DMS production with *Phaeocystis* blooms in the Gulf of Maine and of nutrient salts in the Gulf of Trieste. At the laboratory level, models concerning cell growth rates and the nutrient requirements of implicated species are also quite useful: the incidence of intracellular nitrogen and phosphorus quotas on the rate of cell division; adaptation to nitrogen limitation as a function of temperature; production of allelopathic substances and mucus; transition from autotrophy to mixotrophy; resistance to herbivores grazing pressure, etc. However, it should be kept in mind that these models are limited by their experimental biases. These different aspects of the bloom mechanism revealed the need for more precise definition of spatiotemporal scales and for a greater number of regional models to confirm the apparent spread of these events. In fact, two additional types of models were proposed: climatic ones (proximate diffusion) and those relating to

eutrophication (hierarchical diffusion).

With respect to the influence of human activities, a considerable number of presentations and discussions were devoted to the results of introducing species from one continent into another, whether by ballast dumping from tankers or extensive aquaculture, mainly of bivalves. Effects due to eutrophication were also considered (industrial, domestic and agricultural wastes; acid rain; deforestation; soil leaching; etc.). Failure to take these factors into account when the responsible microalgae produce toxins harmful to marine fauna or the human consumer can lead to considerable economic disruption, particularly financial losses in aquaculture and the appreciable cost of maintaining monitoring networks and treating cases of human poisoning.

The round table discussion on apparent spreading of toxic blooms indicated that the situation is still not clear. Increased awareness among the public and the scientific community as well as development of extensive monitoring networks is undoubtedly providing a more complete picture than that available 20 or 30 years ago. How much of the documented increase in bloom frequency and intensity is real, and how much due to improved monitoring is still unresolved.

Confirmation of the spatiotemporal distribution of a species necessarily requires the study of cysts conserved in sediments (fossilized in the case of the oldest ones), a relatively new scientific approach. New species were reported from different parts of the world, and unknown toxins accumulated by bivalves. Moreover, the increase in the number of toxic and nontoxic blooms seems related to the practice of extensive aquaculture (fish and/or shellfish) in some countries. In this respect, the toxic outbreak in New Zealand in 1992/1993 further illustrates apparent spreading since the neurotoxic shellfish poisoning (NSP) reported there represents its first documented occurrence outside Atlantic waters.

Finally, several investigations involving the association of bacteria with microalgae emphasized the major role played by prokaryotes, in toxin production, cell growth of host algae, and the use of the latter as vectors for pathogenic microorganisms. It was thus shown that several species of marine bacteria from European coasts synthesize toxins that block sodium channels (the same mode of action as paralytic toxins or tetrodotoxins) and that the introduction of associated (extracellular) bacteria potentiates the toxin production of microalgal cultures. More-

over, even though many bacterial species are known to produce paralytic phycotoxins, few are capable of infecting marine organisms.

It was demonstrated that okadaic acid (a diarrhetic toxin produced by *Dinophysis* and some *Prorocentrum*) is detectable both in the microalga, the culture medium and the associated bacteria. The biosynthesis of this toxin and its derivatives by microalgae (as indicated by labeled acetates) seems to follow metabolic pathways similar to those recently found in marine bacteria.

However, in the context of future research in this field, it will be necessary to elucidate the exact role of bacteria and viruses in the marine environment during toxic outbreaks. For example, the production of algicidal substances capable of reducing blooms would be one aspect of this approach.

It may be concluded that, in the current state of our knowledge of the mechanisms of toxic bloom formation, the conceptual tools for description and generalization of the events observed are not always available, despite spectacular advances in understanding of certain ecological interactions. Too many data are still fragmentary or related to situations concerning particular species.

Identification and detection of responsible species

One of the high points of the conference was the presentation by three participants of a new toxic species, the dinoflagellate *Pfiesteria piscimorte*, or 'ambush predator' found along the east coast of America. Depending on whether fish in an estuarine environment are alive or in a state of decomposition, this species produces no fewer than 15 different stages whose successive transformations are induced by thermal and saline shocks or the release of stimulant substances by the prey itself. Nearly all the stages are toxic and display an astonishing saprotrophic activity.

Other communications concerned the development of more efficient detection tools, especially automated ones: image analysis techniques by neuronal networks (back propagation network - BPN), immunological techniques allowing flow cytometry detection after cell labelling, or detection *in situ* of the toxin produced (e.g. brevetoxins), with subsequent determination of cell concentration by reliance on the relation between the number of cells and the quantity of toxin, or direct immunological detection of cells by spectrofluorimetry followed by separa-

tion of sample target species using magnetic processes.

Techniques based on identification of specific proteins (lectins) and fluorescence study of the pigment pattern were also considered, as well as the most suitable sampling methods. A synthesis of knowledge about the number of toxic or bloom-forming species, relative to total worldwide phytoplankton flora, provided several basic principles. In particular, the more diversified an algal class becomes, the greater its number of toxic species or blooms are. A similar result was not obtained for diversification of a genus, but it would appear that the danger of proliferation of new toxic species is far from limited.

Cellular biochemistry and physiology

The communications presented in this session were mainly concerned with biochemistry and the use of genetic engineering tools for species detection, phylogeny and the geographical dissemination of toxic or nontoxic strains of a species or genus. Studies of a physiological nature were more related to the factors involved in toxin production or the improvement of knowledge about the intoxication process. The possible role of okadaic acid on cell division was also considered. In more general terms, the allelopathic relations between toxic and nontoxic species were explored in several communications, particularly for the genera *Chrysochromulina* and *Nitzschia*. With respect to the environmental factors involved in toxin production, the critical role of amino acids (particularly arginine) in the synthesis of paralytic toxins and brevetoxins was considered, as well as the importance of the nitrogen source (NH_4 , NO_3) in the toxicity of species of *Alexandrium*. For *Pyrodinium*, the toxin pattern includes STX (saxi-toxins) but not C toxins, and the total toxin content is modified by variations in temperature or salinity. Finally, toxic processes were described for the genera *Chaetoceros* (fish response to stress by mucus production), *Gymnodinium* (localization of the brevetoxin receptor on the sodium channels) and *Ostreopsis* (activation and inactivation of the sodium channels).

Detection, effects and bioaccumulation of phycotoxins

The development of detection methods is rather closely related to the elucidation of phycotoxin structures. This was clearly demonstrated in the case of maitotoxin and other ciguatera toxins as well as brevetoxins. Derivatives were tested by different types of bioassays, and their

activities analyzed as a function of their affinity for binding to specific sodium channel receptors. A pharmacological test on the specific binding property (direct correlation with toxicity) is used for detection of domoic acid (the toxin of amnesic shellfish poison: ASP), whereas cytotoxicity assays recommended for quantification of maitotoxin (ciguatera) and okadaic acid (diarrhetic poisoning) use hamster fibroblasts. In both cases, automation of the methods by ELISA (Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay) provides appreciable savings in time for detection purposes.

Concerning the bioaccumulation of phycotoxins, we were reminded that bivalve mollusks are not the only vectors of intoxication. Gastropods and certain crustaceans can also accumulate toxins by feeding on contaminated shellfish. Likewise, the ecological impact of microalgal toxicity via the pelagic or benthic food chains shows evidence of contamination of herbivorous and carnivorous fishes by a variety of compounds (DSP, PSP, CFP-Ciguatera fish poisoning). In the most classic case of direct contamination of bivalves, a new okadaic acid derivative (DTX2) was recently found in considerable quantity in European mussels. The rates of accumulation and depuration in shellfish tissues were studied as well for ASP and NSP or PSP toxins. In the last case, the role played by enzymatic degra-

dations in the formation of derivatives of varying toxicity was also demonstrated.

Conclusions

The Sixth International Conference on Toxic Phytoplankton was a valuable source of new information in different fields: the discovery of a new species of dinoflagellate (the 'ambush predator'), the occurrence of novel toxic outbreaks in New Zealand, the presence on European coasts of toxin-producing bacteria blocking sodium channels, the intracellular localization of okadaic acid, etc. Even more than at the Newport conference, we were made aware of the increasing development of detection techniques for toxic species or their metabolites. In this respect, the tools of molecular biology, detection by immunoassay, cytochemical testing and enzymatic inhibition provide investigative approaches which will very shortly improve the efficiency of monitoring networks. Concerning the global spread of blooms and outbreaks, contradictory evidence was presented during discussions. The role of environmental factors is complex and specific, but human activities, at least in introducing species, were clearly implicated.

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Phycotoxin internet

An electronic mailing list has been created on toxic phytoplankton and related subjects, at the Bedford Institute of Oceanography, Dartmouth, N.S., Canada. The list is accessible via the Internet on the address phycotoxins@biome.bio.dfo.ca.

How to subscribe to the list

Anyone interested in joining the list should proceed as follows:

- send a message via Internet to: Majordomo@biome.bio.ns.ca;
- leave the 'subject' line blank;
- in the body of the message the only statement should be: 'Subscribe Phycotoxins'
- if you require further information on the operation of the system, add the word 'help' on a new line.

The system then adds your internet address to the list. Each time a message is posted to Phycotoxins@biome.bio.ns.ca, all addresses on the list will receive a copy.

The list is potentially a very useful tool for worldwide dissemination of information on current developments related to toxic phytoplankton. Similarly, the list can be used as a 'forum' to exchange views, ask questions or advise colleagues working in the same field of interest. Of course, a reply can be sent to the 'list' or to an individual.

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The Philippines:

Social aspects of red tides

Algal blooms can only be considered 'harmful' when they have direct or indirect negative impacts on man.

In 1992, a study was undertaken to (a) describe the knowledge of La Huerta (Paranaque, Manila Bay) residents about the red tide events affecting the area since 1987, (b) determine the general attitudes of the residents toward the events and (c) describe the people's coping mechanisms to the harmful effects of the events. Perceptions and reactions would, of course, be limited to the experiences of the respondents. Results might be beneficial in developing local management schemes specially pertaining to the education of the people and their social welfare/needs. The area has a population of 8,647 with 1,703 households. Ten percent of the households, which is about 170, became the basis for fielding 200 questionnaires. 164 of these were recovered but only 155 were considered, since the rest were not properly and completely answered. Field interviewers visited the respondents at random to establish a rapport with them.

General knowledge of red tide and paralytic shellfish poisoning

One group (called the Pulo residents) has been quite knowledgeable on the cause (the organism) of the discoloration and the poisoning, while the other group (the non-Pulo) attributes the phenomenon to chemical causes.

With regard to the symptoms of paralytic shellfish poisoning, the majority are well aware of the two physical effects – hallucinogenic and paralytic. Eighty nine percent of the respondents believe or know that death could follow if one eats contaminated shellfish. The majority of them, however, did not know that contaminated shellfish could still be alive and even deplete themselves of the toxin.

Concerning first-aid treatments, the majority believe in and have used coconut milk sometimes in combination with sugar. They do not really know the internal effects of these materials including the use of 'baking powder in water'. They are also aware that cooking and drying the shellfish does not lessen the toxicity.

Attitudes toward the event

More than half of the respondents believe that the 'red tides' in their area are an 'inevitable occurrence', while a minority believes that it could be a 'curse'. Reactions to the events include 'sadness' but respondents believe that there is a 'need to

rise above the situation'. A few believe that 'survival' during red tide is everybody's goal because 'only when one has plenty can they help others'. This 'Kanya-kanya' or 'to each his own' system should be stopped, most respondents said, and added that cooperation is most needed during these times. The majority believe that they are not 'panicky' but 'calm' during these situations. As to the information drive regarding the occurrence of the red tides, only 25% of them believe that they have insufficient information.

Coping mechanisms

Fishermen, shellfish divers and sellers said that their incomes were reduced from half to almost nothing during red tides. Some shifted to other jobs like construction drivers, carpenters and mechanics. Others tried buying and selling items like handkerchiefs and towels. Some wives who help their husbands just 'stay at home' during red tides, while some of them sell fruits and cakes or wash clothes for other people.

With regard to the issue of why some of those in the affected areas still eat contaminated shellfish, wholesalers and middlemen take the risk since they would like to prove to buyers that their goods are 'safe'. On the other hand, the majority of the fishermen lead a 'hand to mouth existence' and have to take the chance for there is 'no other food at hand'.

Mendigo (1993) reports that in a related study, the Field Epidemiology

Section of the Department of Health recounted that a number of PSP victims during the 1993 Manila Bay outbreaks had defied the ban on harvest and consumption of contaminated shellfish. One reason given was that they did not believe that the shellfish were poisonous and would like to test this on themselves. An educational campaign is now underway to correct this attitude.

These are social realities brought about by harmful algal blooms. The effects would not be the same if the events occurred in a developed place or country where there are other sources of food and income. It is evident that the people are quite well informed but the social and economic support systems are still lacking despite government financial aids given to these areas. In 1993, about 5 million pesos (approximately \$196,850 in aid was given to Manila Bay red tide affected families. At this point, there is a need for (a) more information campaigns on points not yet clear to the fishermen and other people; (b) development of permanent and feasible alternative sources of income for affected families and (c) research to determine and plan the time of closure and opening of harvest and the management of 'crops' before, during and after red tide events.

Reference

Mendigo, M. A. 1993. *Pyrodinium* Red Tides: How the Philippines Has Coped with a Recurrent Problem. Paper presented in the Pacific Science Inter-Congress held in Okinawa, Japan, June 27-July 3, 1993.

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Harmful algae blooms – Chile Working Group

Harmful algal blooms are not uncommon in Chile and PSP outbreaks in the southernmost part of the fjord ecosystem have been detected again recently. Also, we have noticed harmful effects of the diatom *Leptocylindrus minimus* to fish farms in the Xth Region Inland Sea.

Despite the long geography of our country, with a coast line larger than 4,000 km, we have made the effort to get together. On November 1993 we constituted the Chilean Working Group on Harmful Algal Blooms. The elected coordinator and secretary were Alejandro Clément and Miriam Seguel respectively.

The fundamental goals of the working group are:

- to improve communications among the expertise in the country;

- to develop a national programme taking into consideration the work done by the 'IOC-SCOR Workshop on Programme Development for Harmful Algal Blooms' (IOC Workshop Report N° 80); and
- to improve our national algal blooms data base.

The National Oceanographic Committee (CONA) is the representative of IOC in Chile. The Working Group is therefore under the direction of this committee whose executive secretary is Mr. Mario Cáceres.

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Pseudonitzschia Seriata – A new toxic diatom

After the serious incidents in North America with Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP), a search for potentially toxic diatoms in Danish coastal waters was initiated by the University of Copenhagen, Denmark.

Six species or forms of *Pseudonitzschia* were identified: *P. delicatissima*, *P. fraudulenta*, *P. pseudodelicatissima*, *P. pungens* f. *multiseriata*, *P. pungens* f. *pungens* and *P. seriata*. Surprisingly, *P. seriata* (clone 1877C) from Nivaa Bugt, The Sound, Denmark, was found to produce domoic acid (DA). The identification of the species was kindly confirmed by G.R. Hasle, University of Oslo, Norway. *Pseudonitzschia seriata* has previously been found to be non-toxic

(Bates, 1989, *Can. J. Fish. Aqua. Sci.*, 46, 1203-1215).

The Danish material was isolated into pure culture and grown in F/2 medium at 4°C with a salinity of 20‰ and a 16:8 light:- darkness cycle at 30 $\mu\text{mol photons quanta m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ (Table 1). The highly sensitive FMOC-HPLC method (Pocklington et al., 1990, *Intern. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 38, 351-368) was used for detection of DA.

In *P. seriata*, as in *P. pungens* f. *multiseriata* (Bates, 1989), the toxin was produced only in the stationary growth phase (Lundholm et al., 1994, *Phycologia*, 33, in press). The amount of domoic acid per cell (whole culture) was comparable to the production by *P. pungens* f. *multiseriata* (Table 1). Toxicity has been confirmed in

8-16) and the southern limit of the species in the Western Atlantic is further south (40-45°) than in the Eastern Atlantic (Kiel Bay, 54-55°N) (Hasle, 1972). Records are most numerous from winter and spring: e.g. February to May in the Skagerrak, North Atlantic (Lange et al., 1992, *Sarsia*, 77, 173-187).

Whether *P. seriata* has been involved in domoic acid poisonings is not known. In some records of domoic acid in plankton or mussel samples, the source of DA has never been identified. Thus in March 1989, domoic acid (0.3 - 1.8 ppm) was detected in mussels under the ice at Prince Edward Island, Canada, and in March 1990, domoic acid (60 ng l⁻¹) was found in plankton below the ice. *P. pungens* f. *multiseriata* was not present in the samples (Pauley et al., 1993, *Toxic Phytoplankton Blooms in the Sea*, 311-316). However,

Shellfish poisoning: Boy dies and 13 treated

In January this year, in Kota Kinabalu, Malaysia, a six year-old boy died while 13 people received emergency treatment at the Queen Elizabeth Hospital (QEH), from paralytic shellfish poisoning.

Sabah Medical and Health Services Director, Dr. M. Chan, warned the general public against collecting and consuming shellfish found at Kampung Gentisen, in Sepangar Bay.

The deceased was on a picnic with his family at the Kampung Gentisen beach where they collected some shellfish for their Sunday lunch. The father later noticed his son was sick and immediately rushed him to hospital, where he was pronounced dead on arrival. Thirteen others were admitted to the hospital for treatment.

According to Chan, one of the victims bought the shellfish from the Menggal market, believed to have been collected from Kampung Gentisen.

The signs and symptoms of paralytic shellfish poisoning are nausea, vomiting, dizziness, weakness, numbness of the limbs, tongue and lips, and difficulty in breathing. He advised anyone suffering from such symptoms after eating shellfish to seek immediate treatment at the nearest hospital.

The department's health education unit is distributing leaflets on paralytic shellfish poisoning to residents in the affected areas. Talks on health education are also being given, with a warning against collecting and eating shellfish.

Chan said the Health Department would continue to investigate and monitor the situation, with the cooperation of the Fisheries Department.

Extract from Daily Express, 19 January 1994.

Table 1
P. seriata – Concentration of cells and domoic acid in stationary growth phase.
The stationary phase was reached at day 20.

Days of growth	Concentration of cells* ml ⁻¹	Domoic acid ng ml ⁻¹	Domoic acid pg cell ^{-1**}
18	23200	4.5	0.2
25	30870	6.9	0.22
32	39728	14.3	0.36
39	48083	36.9	0.77
43	48900	51.8	1.1
48	50400	92	1.8
53	38533	126.3	3.3
62	13747	188.3	13.7

* At least 400 cells ml⁻¹ were counted.

** Based on whole culture (cells plus medium).

two other isolates (1877A and 1877B) from the same locality.

The following characteristics may be used to identify *P. seriata*, formerly *Nitzschia seriata* (Hasle, 1993, *Beih. N. Hedw.*, 106, 315-321): Seen in valve view, the frustules are asymmetric and 5-8 μm wide. In electron microscopy the lack of a central nodulus is characteristic and frustules possess 4 (3-5) rows of small poroids in the striae and 14-18 interstriae in 10 μm (Hasle, 1965, *Vid. Akad. Skr. I. M.-N. Kl. Ny serie*, N°18, and own unpubl. observations).

P. seriata is a cold-water species, which occurs in both neritic and oceanic areas. It has been found only in the Northern Hemisphere (Hasle, 1972, *Beih. N. Hedw.*, 39; Hasle, 1976, *Deep-Sea Res.*, 23, 319-338). Records from the Southern Hemisphere or from warm waters seem to be misidentifications (Hasle, 1972).

P. seriata is a common species in the Arctic (Smith et al., 1994, *J. Phycol.*, 30,

one of the most prominent species in the 1990 event was *P. seriata*. Since cell concentrations were very low (max. 2.5 $\times 10^4$ cells l⁻¹), it: 'would have to be a strong producer [of DA] (e.g. ~2 pg cell⁻¹, which is characteristic of *N. pungens* f. *multiseriata* in culture) to account for the observed DA levels.' (Pauley et al., 1993, *op. cit.*, p. 313). These concentrations are consistent with our findings.

The finding of *P. seriata* as a producer of domoic acid has consequences for the future monitoring. Further investigations especially on the fate of toxic diatoms in the food chain are urgently needed.

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Fish kills and *Gymnodinium* cf. *nagasakiense* in Corsica (France)

A *Gymnodinium* cf. *nagasakiense* bloom occurred in the coastal lagoon of Diane, located on the coast of Corsica, a Mediterranean island (Figure 1). It was the cause of some fish kills, which led to the study of different aspects of the production of exotoxins by this alga.

The fish deaths occurred on 24 September 1993, preceded by strong winds on September 23rd. Histological examination of the gills of moribund fish showed a congestion, a hemorrhage and a slight subepithelial oedema.

In one day, about 500 kg each of sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) and sea bream (*Boops boops*) died. This is a low proportion of the annual production in this area (170 tons/year), but if we consider the mortalities of *Ostrea gigas* which occurred in 1987 and 1989 in the lagoon, these recent losses constitute an indicator of a persistent critical bloom situation.

Present at low levels in the summer and associated with Prorocentrales and Silicoflagellates, *G. cf. nagasakiense* began to dominate the phytoplankton after 14 September. The maximal density: $2.7 \cdot 10^6$ cells/litre was observed on 18 October. Then the *Gymnodinium* population decreased while *Thalassiosira* spp. prevailed at 80%. In late October the bloom declined entirely, probably because of very bad meteorological conditions. The maximum cell density followed a temperature plateau of about 21°C, and a moderate decrease in dissolved oxygen saturation (Figure 2).

During this event, seawater quality was followed in terms of its standard hydrobiological composition as well as its allelopathic and ichthyotoxic potency.

Seawater containing 4,000 *Gymnodinium* cells/litre was tested with and

Fig. 1. ● = Geographical site and sampling station.

without filtration on GF/F filters (Whatman). The toxin affected the 9-day larvae of *Pecten maximus* inducing a 40% death rate within 9 days of contact with the toxic seawater. The size of the surviving larvae was 30 µm, inferior to the control obtained with uncontaminated seawater.

Allelopathic properties of lagoon seawater, which contained 4,000 *Gymnodinium* cells/litre, were effective towards the diatom *Chaetoceros gracile* growth.

Filtered seawater and the *G. cf. nagasakiense* cell were studied in terms of their lipid components. The amount of octadecapentaenoic acid, a highly toxic polyunsaturated fatty acid, was elevated in samples (filtered seawater and cellular

Fig. 2. Temperature, dissolved oxygen saturation and cell concentration at surface.

1994 PSP Cases in the Philippines and Malaysia

Despite the imposition of a ban on shellfish gathering from affected areas, 23 people have been hospitalized for paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) after consuming infected 'tahong' (mussels) from Limay and Orion in Bataan, Manila Bay as of 16 June 1994.

The Governor of Bataan, Enrique Garcia, directed health officers to undertake a mass information campaign on the temporary ban on the harvest, sale and consumption of mussels from 3 towns (Orion, Limay and Mariveles). He noted that yearly, even in red tide months, many still insist on eating mussels. In the Philippines, toxicity levels for banning has been set at higher than 40 µg/100g of mussels. This increases the recorded PSP cases in the Philippines to 1,488 since 1983.

Earlier in Kota Kinabalu, Malaysia, the Daily Express reported on 19 January, 1994, that a 6 year old boy died and 13 others were treated for PSP. *Pyrodinium bahamense* var. *compressum* has been affecting the waters of Malaysia and the Philippines since the 1980's. (See article on this case on previous page.)

extracts) which contained significant concentrations of *Gymnodinium* cf. *nagasakiense* cells.

This alga very closely resembles the Channel and Oceanic species but it is not definitively identified as such.

The authors also allude to the possible importance of other biological factors, including preconditioning of the water by other phytoplankton species composition, and the interaction between hydrographic features and environmental parameters (temperature and oxygen content), to explain the occurrence of high concentration of *G. cf. nagasakiense* cells in the surface water.

This event was studied, for water sampling and physico-chemical data, by the IFREMER Pelagic Ecology Laboratory, with the participation of the IFREMER Coastal Laboratories of Santa Maria Poggio, Concarneau and Toulon.

Geneviève Arzul, Guy Bodennec, Evelyne Erard, Patrick Gentien, IFREMER Centre de BREST-DEL, BP 70-29280 Plouzane, France.

IOC Publications

Available free of charge

The publications listed below are available free of charge from the IOC. Please address requests for these publications, as well as for extra copies of issues 1-8 of *Harmful Algae News* to: IOC Secretariat, Harmful Algal Bloom Programme, UNESCO, 1 rue Miollis, 75732 Paris Cedex 15, France.

Summary Report of the IOC-FAO Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms, Second Session, Paris, 14-16 October 1993.

International Workshop on Training Requirements in the Field of Eutrophication in Semi-Enclosed Seas and Harmful Algal Blooms, Germany, September 1992. *IOC Workshop Report* No. 94.

Assessment and Monitoring of Large Marine Ecosystems. Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission, 1993. *IOC/INF-942*.

The following copies are also available for scientists in developing countries (priority to libraries):

Proceedings of International Symposium on Marine Biotoxins, France, 1991. Ed. J. Marc Fremy. Courtesy of Centre National d'Études Vétérinaires et Alimentaires, France.

Biotoxines aquatiques (eau de mer et eau douce). Critères d'hygiène de l'environnement 37. International Programme on Chemical Safety (IPCS), World Health Organization, Geneva, 1986.

Future events

SEPTEMBER 94

13th International Diatom Symposium, 1-7 September, Acquafredda di Maratea, Italy. *Contact*: Jean Gilder Congressi snc., Via G. Quagliariello 35/E, I-80131 Napoli, Italy; tel: (39-81) 546 3779 or 545 4617; fax: (39-81) 546 3781.

4th International Symposium of the AOAC Europe Section – 'Food and Feed Analysis: A focus on methods with minimal hazards to health and environment', 29-30 September, Nyon, Switzerland. *Contact*: AOAC Europe Section Symposium, Dr. T. Rihs, Swiss Federal Research Station for Animal Production, CH-1725 Posieux, Switzerland; tel: (41-37) 877 111; fax: (41-37) 877 400.

OCTOBER 94

11th World Congress on Animal, Plant and Microbial Toxins, 2-7 October, Tel Aviv, Israel. *Contact*: KENES - Organizers of Congresses and Tour Operators Ltd., P.O. Box 50006, Tel Aviv 61500, Israel; tel: (972-3) 5140014; fax: (972-3) 5175674/660325; telex: 341171 kens il.

NOVEMBER 94

IOC International Oceanographic Conference – 'Towards sustainable use of the oceans and coastal zones', 7-12

November, Lisbon, Portugal. *Contact*: Secretary, IOC, 1 rue Miollis, 75732 Paris cedex 15, France; fax (33-1) 4056 9316.

JUNE 95

1995 Gordon Conference on Mycotoxins and Phycotoxins – 'Frontiers in Science', 25-30 June, New Plymouth, USA. *Contact*: Daniel G. Baden (Conference Chair), NIEHS MFBS Center, University of Miami RSMAS, 4600 Rickenbacker Causeway, Miami, FL 33149, USA; tel: (1-305) 361 4738; fax: (1-305) 361 4001; or Wanda M. Haschek-Hock (Vice Chair and Poster Sessions), Dept. of Veterinary Pathobiology, University of Illinois, 2001 S. Lincoln Avenue, Urbana, IL 61801, USA; tel: (1-217) 333 4755.

JULY 95

2nd International Conference on Pelagic Biogeography (ICoPB), 10-14 July, Amsterdam, The Netherlands. *Contact*: Institut voor Taxonomische Zoölogie, Zoölogisch Museum, Mauritskade 57, Postbus 94766, 1090 GT Amsterdam, The Netherlands.

Symposium on Changes in the North Sea Ecosystem and their Causes: Århus 1975 Revisited, 11-14 July, Århus, Denmark. Deadline for submission of papers and posters: **1 October 1994**. *Contact*: General Secretary, ICES, Palægade 2-4, 1261 Copenhagen K, Denmark; tel: (45) 15 42 25; fax: (45) 33 93 42 15.

7th International Conference on Toxic Marine Phytoplankton, 12-16 July, Sendai, Japan. *Contact*: Dr. Takeshi Yasumoto, Conference Convener, 7th International Conference on Toxic Marine Phytoplankton, Dept. of Applied Biological Chemistry, Faculty of Agriculture, Tohoku University, Tsutsumidori-Amamiya, Aoba-ku, Sendai 981, Japan; tel: (81-22) 272 4321; fax: (81-22) 275 3606 or 272 1870.

Errata for HAN n°. 7

◆ The article 'Ciguatera Management Workshop, Bribie Island, Australia' was authored by Dr. Richard J. Lewis. Only that part headed 'Toxin Action' was written by Dr. J-P. Vernoux. Our apologies for the confusion.

◆ In the article 'South Korean oysters gave ASP symptoms', the oysters eaten were from South Korea. They were eaten in U.S.A.

Eds.

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

This issue was compiled and edited by Tim Wyatt and Yolanda Pazos, Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Eduardo Cabello 6, 36208 Vigo, Spain. Tel.: (34-86) 23 19 30 / 23 19 73; fax: (34 86) 29 27 62

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